

APPLICATION OF HAMMICK AND ANDREWS' EQUATION TO BINARY AND TERNARY MIXTURES

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Hammick and Andrews' equation is extended to ternary mixture of water, urea and acetamide. The values of parachor of acetamide, urea and cane sugar give lower values than the calculated ones.

Hammick and Andrews have shown for binary mixture that the expression

$$P_m = (1-x) P + xP$$

gives the parachor P_x of dissolved solid, where P_m , and x have usual significance.

If additive law can be extended for ternary mixture the observed value of parachor for solution P_m is given by

$$P_m = (1-x-y) P + xP_x + yP_y$$

where P_x , P_y and P are the parachors of the solutes and solvent respectively and x and y are the molar fraction of the solutes present in $(1-x-y)$ moles of solvent. P_m is given by

$$P_m = \frac{M}{d} r^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

where r is the surface tension of the solution, d , the density of the solution and M is the mean molecular weight of the solution given by

$$M = (1-x-y)M + xM_x + yM_y$$

where M_x and M_y are the molecular weights of solutes and M is the molecular weight of solvent.

Parachor of acetamide is determined in the fused state by Sudgen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1177) and by Turner and Merry (*ibid.*, 1910, 97, 2068). The value is 148.8. The calculated value is 150.8. The average value in solution as obtained by us is 130, much lower. The same is true of urea. The calculated value is 141.2, but the observed value increases with concentration and is about 118. Assuming this value for urea in solution the value for acetamide in ternary mixture is calculated. It comes out to be 134, very near to the value obtained in solution. In the following tables parachor of water has been taken to be 52.2.

TABLE I

Parachor of acetamide

	$x=0.1792$, $M_m=25.34$				$x=0.2285$, $M_m=27.35$				$x=0.2818$, $M_m=29.55$			
Temp.	Density.	r .	P_m .	P_x .	Density.	r .	P_m .	P_x .	Density.	r .	P_m .	P_x .
20°	1.049	54.12	65.51	126.4	1.053	52.48	69.92	129.9	1.059	50.74	74.47	131.2
30	1.043	52.06	65.25	125.02	1.047	50.48	69.63	128.6	1.053	48.77	74.15	130.0
40	1.038	50.82	65.18	124.6	1.041	49.00	69.50	128.7	1.047	46.99	73.87	129.1
50	1.033	49.11	64.94	123.0	1.036	46.76	69.00	125.8	1.041	45.36	73.65	128.3

Parachor of urea

	$x=0.0453$, $M_m=19.81$				$x=0.0792$, $M_m=21.33$				$x=0.0987$, $M_m=22.15$			
Temp.	Density.	r .	P_m .	P_x .	Density.	r .	P_m .	P_x .	Density.	r .	P_m .	P_x .
20°	1.059	69.66	54.05	93.05	1.083	70.76	57.12	114.3	1.095	70.76	58.69	117.9
30	1.054	68.06	53.96	91.06	1.079	69.1	57.02	113.1	1.090	68.55	58.49	115.9
40	1.051	65.94	53.63	83.8	1.074	67.05	56.83	110.7	1.085	66.49	58.12	114.5
50	1.047	64.06	53.52	81.8	1.071	65.1	56.57	107.4	1.083	65.04	58.12	112.2

	$x=0.1501$, $M_m=24.27$				$x=0.1245$, $M_m=23.23$			
Temp.	Density.	r .	P_m .	P_x .	Density.	r .	P_m .	P_x .
20°	1.132	70.04	62.01	117.6	1.113	70.44	60.47	118.6
30	1.127	68.41	61.93	117.0	1.109	68.32	60.24	116.8
40	1.122	66.36	61.73	115.7	1.106	66.19	59.92	114.2
50	1.117	64.51	61.58	114.7	1.102	64.68	59.8	113.2

TABLE I (contd.)

Parachor of cane sugar

$x=0.0216$, $M_m=25.02$.				$x=0.0257$, $M_m=26.35$.				$x=0.0377$, $M_m=30.27$.				
Temp	Density.	r .	P_m .	P_x .	Density.	r .	P_m .	P_x .	Density.	r .	P_m .	P_x .
20°	1.148	70.46	63.13	558.5	1.167	70.63	65.46	567.8	1.217	71.58	72.35	586.6
30	1.144	68.21	62.84	544.9	1.163	68.80	65.25	560.0	1.213	69.24	71.97	576.6
40	1.141	66.59	62.73	539.8	1.159	67.17	65.11	554.6	1.208	67.72	71.90	574.6
50	1.136	66.31	62.70	536.6	1.156	66.16	65.07	553.8	1.205	65.22	71.66	568.4

The cane sugar is $C_{12}H_{22}O_{11}$. Hence its parachor should be $P=12C+22H+C_{12}H_{22}O_{11}$
 $110 + \text{Ring of six} + \text{Ring of five} = 57.6 + 375.2 + 220 + 6.1 + 8.5 = 667.4$

Parachor of a Ternary mixture—Water, Acetamide and Urea

TABLE II

2.725 G. of urea and 5.354 g. of acetamide dissolved in 7.5025 g. of water. x (acetamide) = 0.1640. y (urea) = 0.0821. $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.7539. $M_m = 28.18$.

Temp.	Density.	r .	P_m .	P_x .
20°	1.070	52.08	70.74	132.2
30	1.066	50.07	70.33	130.7
40	1.060	48.44	70.3	131.3
50	1.056	47.18	69.93	130.2

TABLE III

4.4160 G. of urea, 5.3444 g. of acetamide dissolved in 7.4446 g. of water. x (acetamide) = 0.1567. y (urea) = 0.1274. $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.7159. $M_m = 29.78$.

Density.	r .	P_m .	P_x .
1.095	52.58	73.24	133.3
1.090	50.67	72.91	131.7
1.083	49.39	72.274	131.6
1.078	47.77	72.64	131.8

TABLE IV

2.7626 G. of urea, 9.852 g. of acetamide dissolved in 7.4617 g. of water. x (acetamide) = 0.2627. y (urea) = 0.0737. $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.6636. $M_m = 31.87$.

Temp.	Density.	r .	P_m .	P_x .
20°	1.071	48.94	78.66	134.4
30	1.069	46.77	77.98	132.4
40	1.053	45.60	77.69	131.7
50	1.056	44.10	77.78	132.7

TABLE V

3.5402 G. of urea and 7.2818 g. of acetamide dissolved in 7.423 g. of water. x (acetamide) = 0.2875. y (urea) = 0.0992. $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.6933. $M_m = 30.67$.

Density.	r .	P_m .	P_x .
1.078	53.92	76.35	136.5
1.072	51.75	76.03	136.1
1.068	50.06	75.82	136.5
1.063	48.49	75.58	135.7

These results clearly show that the law can be extended to ternary mixtures. Clearly the values assumed are those which were obtained in solution. The coincidence between the results obtained in mixture and when studied alone in solution is enough to prove the applicability.